

Desire for Unique Consumer Product as a Mediator between Consumer Innovativeness and New Product Adoption Behavior

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Abstract

This particular review designed to measure mediating role of desire for unique consumer product between consumer innovativeness and new product adoption behavior. A survey methodology was used to collect the data from the students of different universities. Structural regression (SR) model was used to test the proposed hypothesis. The results display that although consumer innovativeness has significant influence on desire for unique consumer product and also on the variables of new product adoption behavior such as consumer novelty seeking for the early product adoption behavior of the customers and consumer independent judgement making for the later product adoption behavior of the customers. The result also shows that desire for unique consumer product is not playing the mediating role between the consumer innovativeness and new product adoption behavior because desire for unique consumer product has no significant influence on the variables of new product adoption behavior.

Introduction

Throughout the last decades, researchers have made pragmatic that that new product adoption behavior had confined is product diffusion process (Rogers, 1995). For adopting the new product consumer innovativeness plays important role (Hirschman, 1980). According to Rogers (1995) innovators are actually the earliest adopter of new products. Similarly, Midgley and Dowling (1978) acknowledged consumer innovativeness seeing that the diploma that an individual would make development choices individually with the disseminated connection with other individuals. Studies indicate that new product adoption behavior (NPAB) is like a progressive habits i. age., “actualized innovativeness,” as well as the actual order regarding brand-completely new concepts and ideas.

In line with Harris & Lynn, (1996) Customers can differ from the individual objectives, the actual achievement and also property regarding companies, consumer products and also activities that may also be pressed by handful of people and also label this kind of objective driven as the desire for unique consumer product (DUCP). In line with Fromkin (2002), the necessity regarding individuality thrusts your specific to help make a

distinction himself/herself with the property regarding odd things.

A lot of scientific research witnessed empirically the actual influence regarding individual qualities with new product habits by paying attention to the actual mediating part regarding vicarious variables with new product habits although there is a limitation that they can assessed the new product adoption habits as a result of cross sectional data and also occasion regarding adoption with the product although no one used the appropriate scale regarding new product adoption behavior. It has already been witnessed that desire for unique consumer product performs a mediating part from the new product adoption behavior (Tian et 's., 2001).

To understand the consumer habits, researchers include performed the actual experiments around the younger older consumers. Grant and also Waite (2003) offers acknowledged some factors to complete research around the younger consumers. Primary, younger consumers type their unique attitude and also intake pattern to build individuality. Next, younger consumer could impact the actual buy decision with the people. Thirdly, they may be the one that could alter the actual way of life and also contemporary society. Finally inside a marketing perspective they may be

the particular segment having potent investing capacity within their individual technique.

As a result the objective of this kind of review should be to find the actual mediating part with the consumer's desire to have unique product around the connection regarding consumer innovativeness and also new product adoption behavior i. age. early on adoption and also after adoption with the product with the Pakistani college or university students.

Literature Review

Consumer Innovativeness

The literary works shows there are two principles regarding innovativeness related to the new product adoption habits; is innate consumer innovativeness as well as other is actually domain specific innovativeness.

Im et al. (2003) decided consumer innovativeness as the qualities of man or women to get new products well as brand rather than the current product as well as brand before the people. Mowen (2000) perceived that as the situational attribute that final result at a consumers characteristics and also learning history which often has a bearing on the actual habits regarding consumer across intake situation. Goldsmith and also Foxall (2003) described consumer innovativeness seeing that globalized innovativeness and also differentiated that on the domain specific innovativeness that may be particular to the product as well as brand group. Some scientific researchers have described the consumer innovativeness as the details information and also seeking the modern activities (Goldsmith, 1984).

Im et al. (2007) dispute that moderating variables this kind of advertising vicarious innovativeness performs substantial part from the new product adoption behavior. Ruvio and also Shoham (2007) dispute that consumer inventions is among the significant supply for your organizations even though adding the new product out there and as well performs a critical part from the diffusion with the product. Goldsmith (2001) described

innovators seeing that well-informed, large consumers with the services and also cost insensitive.

Researchers include accentuated that consumer innovators are people who receive information regarding the new product though unique searching for and still provide the details to their guy consumers by discussing their own information and also activities (Goldsmith, Flynn and also Goldsmith, 2003).

Likewise, Ruvio and also Shoham (2008) dispute that consumer innovators are part products and also judgment leaders for your after consumers and also impact their own new product adoption behavior.

New Product adoption behavior

Researchers include new product adoption behavior with the consumer seeing that innovative behavior with the consumers and as well referred to as this kind of seeing that actualized innovativeness and also actualized innovativeness may be the strategy of getting brand new concepts in regards to the product as well as companies agreed to the customers can use (Midgley & Dowling, 1978).

For the base of the behavior perspective, scientific researches include operationalized the actual innovative behavior directly into about three techniques. Primary, a lot of researchers assessed some time regarding adoption regarding product of one consumer and also weighed against some time regarding adoption with the other customers (Rogers and also Shoemaker, 1971). This method incorporates a disadvantage regarding using the single product and also produces the actual recollect dilemma (Midgley and also Dowling, 1978). Second, a lot of researchers devoted to the actual cross sectional procedure by which a fresh product listing was presented with to help respondent to point that product they not long ago acquired (Goldsmith, Freiden and also Eastman, 1995). Using this method boasts the situation with the biasness. Your third solution to calculate new product adoption behavior is actually buy intentions (Holak and also Lehman, 1970). Using this method

boasts disadvantage regarding computing intension definitely not the specific habits.

Midgley and also Dowling (1995) proposed that consumer novelty seeking for is actually favorably related with earlier stages regarding adoption habits even though consumer independent judgment making is actually related with the actual after stages regarding new product adoption behavior with the consumers.

Consumer novelty seeking for (CNS) is understood to be the actual desire to research the modern information regarding the new product (Hirschman's, 1980).

Hirschman's (1980) in addition identifies new product adoption behavior seeing that consumers' inspiration to get info relating to services as a result of commonly accessible alternatives such as advertising and marketing, primary product marketing, as well as several forms of enterprise marketing and sales communications.

Some researchers have described that consumer actively seeks the details on the people when creating new product acquiring decision. They have in addition described that often early on adopters acquire the actual pitfalls regarding new product acquiring without having getting details and also assistance from one other solutions (Midgley and also Dowling, 1980).

Desire for unique consumer product

Customers can differ from the individual objectives the actual achievement and also property regarding companies, consumer products and also activities that may also be pressed by handful of people (Lynn & Harris, 1997). All of us label this kind of objective driven, the actual desire for unique consumer product (DUCP) as the individual variations variable. In line with Roehrich (2002), the necessity regarding individuality thrusts your specific to help make a distinction himself/herself with the property regarding odd things.

Roehrich (2002) there are about three proposed penalties with the desire for individuality: very first may be the absence of curiosity about because of result of people; subsequent, the actual

desire regarding definitely not pursuing regulations always; plus the next is actually publically viewpoints defended having one's earned willingness. Desire for individuality may be the results of societal comparison process which can be relied with self-perceived quantity individual's individuality which can be related with people. This is actually the societal comparison process through which communities as well as men and women examine themselves and also because of this that they start using a framework regarding reference point where upcoming decision doing habits is happening. Suitable state may be the place having that current state is actually in contrast and yes it depends on the actual individual's energy regarding desire for individuality. An individual's self-perceived quantity individuality is actually that with a latest place of your time an individual feels to help resemble him/herself having people (Burns & Warren, 1995).

Roehrich (2002) services are used by traders who are loaded with desire for individuality. Through this kind of it is usually concluded that innovativeness offers main antecedent which can be desire for individuality. For the reason that desire for individuality could be very easily pleased as a result of innovativeness and also subsequently independence in judgment is essential in desire for individuality which can be required regarding modern acquiring (Roehrich, 2002).

Folks try to create themselves not the same as people this kind of realizes that they have necessary for individuality and also by this kind of advocates declare that folks carry out contain the desire for individuality. (Fromkin, 1972)

Innovators are the individuals which take up new product even though usually it doesn't achieve a sudden and also frequent endorsement, innovators impact after adopters (Rogers, 1983). It can be explained that these people are continuously are looking for brand new delight and also brand new product, and yes it will become more challenging to help speak the actual newness and also inspire men and women to get the item as well as brand to meet the necessity regarding individuality. This particular causes conclusion that want regarding individuality will have a good mediating impact on consumer's

choice regarding, and also attractiveness rankings regarding, graphic product newness (Tian et al., 2001). On the basis of theory and literature, researcher has proposed the following hypothesis.

H1: Consumer innovativeness has positive influence on desire for unique consumer product

H2: Consumer innovativeness has positive influence on the variables of new product adoption behavior such as consumer novelty seeking and independent judgement making.

H3: Desire for unique consumer product has positive influence towards variables of new product adoption behavior such as consumer novelty seeking and independent judgement making.

H4: Desire for unique consumer product mediates the relationship between consumer innovativeness and variables of new product adoption behavior such as consumer novelty seeking and independent judgement making.

Methodology

Results

First of all analyst performed CFA so that you can check out the actual reliability and also validity with the well toned scale found in this kind of review. Researchers used several types of healthy indices regarding credit reporting the outcome regarding Structural Formula Branding (SEM) although according to Schreiber et al., (2006), analyst thought we would employ some important healthy indices, i.e., $CMIN/df < 3$, $TLI > 0.90$, $CFI > 0.90$, and also $RMSEA < .08$. Confirmatory factor analysis was used for measures regarding consumer innovativeness (CI), Desire to have unique consumer expert ducts (DUCP), Consumer novelty seeking (CNS) and also Consumer Independent judgement (CIJM). Right after jogging the actual CFA, the actual analyst observed very poor healthy indices, although immediately after watching the actual element filling of measures with the constructs, analyst lowered 1 components of CI, 5 components of CNS, 1 item regarding CIJM, and also 2 components of DUCP one by one respectively because of the lower element filling (i.e., $< .50$) after which it went CFA again. The results had been towards the proposed healthy indices although immediately after correlating the actual diversities regarding way of measuring problems one by one getting M. I value (i.e., > 10). In line with the advice regarding Kline (2011) the actual standardized element loadings of all indicators had been observed over the actual value $> .50$ and after this the researcher found going fitness of indices such as $CMIN/df = 2.5$, $TLI = 0.92$, $CFI = 0.93$, and also $RMSEA = 0.06$

The goal of study is to find out the role of desire for unique consumer product as a mediator between the consumer innovativeness and new product adoption behavior. A questionnaire was developed for the collection of data from the students of different universities of Pakistan. A convenient sampling technique was used for the collection of data. For measuring the desire for unique consumer product, scale was adopted from the study of Lynn and also Harris (1997), for measuring the consumer innovativeness scale was adopted from the study of Hofacker (1991) and for measuring the new product adoption behavior, scale was adopted from the study of Manning, Bearden and also Madden (1995). For collection of data researcher distributed 350 questionnaires and 280 questionnaires were returned back. After screening the data from missing values, aberrant values and outliers only 260 cases were found useable for the study. All the proposed objectives were analyzed by using the SPSS 18 and AMOS 18.

The detailed mean, standard deviation and correlation summary are demonstrated in table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics and inter-correlations summary

	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1. Gender	NA	NA									
2. Age	1.70	.64	.32**								
3. Qualification	2.91	.84	.15*	.70**							
4. Marital Status	1.16	.37	.29**	.37**	.21**						
5. Income	2.72	1.18	.099	.96	.69	.15					
6. CI	3.66	.93	.15*	.161	.53	.23	.17	0.89			
7. CNS	3.48	.91	.179**	.012	.18	.046	.27	.52**	0.74		
8. CIJM	2.65	.89	.12	.045	.32	.105	.72	.42**	.71**	0.88	
9. DUCP	3.45	.69	.19	.023	.52	.32	.025	.41**	.38	.23	0.84

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). CI= Consumer Innovativeness; DUCP = Desire for Unique Consumer product; CIJM = Consumer Independent Judgment making; CNS = consumer Novelty Seeking

After finding the correlation of the variables, researchers also find out the reliability and validity of the all variables. The results shown in table 2 demonstrated that CR is the composite reliability of the variables and if the average variance extracted is greater than 0.50 and less than the CR, it will represent the convergent validity and if the MSV and ASV are less than the AVE, then it will represent the discriminate validity.

Table 2: Reliability and validity

	CR	AVE	MSV	ASV
CI	0.89	0.61	0.28	0.21
DUCP	0.74	0.48	0.17	0.10
CIJM	0.88	0.66	0.49	0.24
CNS	0.84	0.63	0.49	0.29

CI= Consumer Innovativeness; DUCP = Desire for Unique Consumer product; CIJM = Consumer Independent Judgment making; CNS = consumer Novelty Seeking; CR = Composite Reliability; AVE = Average Variance Extracted; MSV = Maximum Shared Variance; ASV= Average Shared Variance

Not like various other scientific researches analyst used SEM not just regarding confirmatory element examination but used that regarding speculation examining as a result of structural regression. The largest advantage of SEM is actually who's has the capacity to defeat the actual way of measuring problem having inside a record brand because this kind of can't be done as a result of a number of regressions.

Table 3: Regression Weights

DUCP	New Product Adoption Behavior								
	CNS			CIJM					
	P.E	S.E.	P	P.E	S.E.	P	P.E	S.E.	P
CI	0.343	0.058	0.000	0.514	0.084	0.000	0.629	0.09	0.000
DUCP	--	--	--	0.47	0.147	0.509	0.219	0.62	0.412
R ²	0.39			0.23			0.35		

CI= Consumer Innovativeness; DUCP = Desire for Unique Consumer product; CIJM = Consumer Independent Judgment making; CNS = consumer Novelty Seeking

The results in table 3 demonstrated that hypothesis H1 and H2 are supported because consumer innovativeness has positive relationship with desire for unique consumer product (unstandardized $\beta = .343$; S.E = .058; $p = 0.000$), and consumer innovativeness also have significant influence on the variables of new product adoption behavior such as consumer independent judgment making and consumer novelty seeking (unstandardized $\beta = .62$; S.E = .09; $p = 0.000$) and (unstandardized $\beta = .51$; S.E = .08; $p = 0.000$) respectively. However, no support was found for H3 because desire for unique consumer product has no positive impact on the variables of new product adoption behavior such as consumer independent judgment making (unstandardized $\beta = .219$; S.E = .62; $p = 0.412$), and on consumer novelty seeking (unstandardized $\beta = .47$; S.E = .147; $p = 0.509$) respectively.

Similarly, no support was found for the H4 that was Desire for unique consumer product mediates the relationship between consumer innovativeness and variables of new product adoption behavior such as consumer novelty seeking and independent judgment making. The results are shown in table 4.

Table 4: Mediation Results

	New Product Adoption Behavior							
	CNS				CIJM			
	P.E	SE	Lower	Upper	P.E	SE	Lower	Upper
Total effect	0.23	.06	-.0335	0.224	0.17	0.148	0.228	0.218
Direct Effect	0.07	0.19	0.294	0.482	0.15	0.17	0.257	0.335
Indirect Effect	0.16	0.17	-0.341	0.068	0.68	0.23	0.015	-0.025

I.V = Consumer Innovativeness; Mediator = Desire for unique consumer product

Discussion

This particular review empirically examined the actual influence regarding consumer innovativeness with new product adoption behavior in 2 stages i.e., consumer novelty seeking and consumer independent judgment making. Unique observed that consumer innovativeness offers optimistic have an effect on previously new product adoption as a result of unique searching for because older consumers try to take up the modern product prior to whilst. The studies of the review are in line with the sooner scientific researches including Midgley and also Dowling (1993). The learning in addition exhibited that consumer innovativeness offers damaging affiliation having consumer independent judgment making as the students comprehend that after adoption with the new product seriously isn't can be found in the new product adoption habits. Individuals might also comprehend that consumer innovativeness should be only whenever a purchaser take up the new product early on as opposed to people. So they really think of is actually negatively. Although Tian et 's., (2001) argued that want regarding

individuality will have a good mediating impact on consumer's choice regarding, and also attractiveness rankings regarding, graphic product newness however in this kind of review desire to have the initial consumer product seriously isn't mediating the relationship regarding consumer innovativeness and also new product adoption behavior. That is a result of that literary works offers relatively proven that desire to have the initial consumer product trigger consumer innovativeness and that bring about the new product adoption habits.

Although, consumer innovativeness offers optimistic substantial have an effect on previously adoption with the new product nevertheless it contains the poor connection. It is because due the individual features with the consumers and also common conceptual habits with the consumer between innovativeness and also new product adoption behavior.

Managerial Implications

This particular review is going to be very therapeutic for distinct national and also international firms doing business in Pakistan. This particular review offers investigated the actual impact regarding consumer innovativeness with

services adoption habits and also it'll be very therapeutic for the actual internet marketers to target their own customers within the effective approach. By using this kind of review income managers could enrich their own income swiftly by focusing on and also segmenting the actual prospective customers. This particular review may also be very therapeutic for the actual students and also course instructors even though discussing the actual principles regarding innovativeness with new product adoption behavior within their marketing classes and can enrich their own familiarity with decision doing methods of Pakistani customers. Additionally this kind of review will provide helpful tips range regarding upcoming experiments within this area regarding marketing

Conclusion

This particular review empirically investigated the actual mediating part regarding desire for unique consumer product between consumer innovativeness and also new product adoption behavior (early adoption and also after adoption with the products). The results exhibited that consumer innovativeness offers optimistic have an effect on the actual desire to have the initial product although desire to have the initial consumer product doesn't have any substantial connection with consumer independent judgement making that is the construct regarding after adoption with the product. It has already been seen in this kind of review that consumer innovativeness offers damaging affiliation having consumer independent judgement making. Benefits have proven that desire for unique consumer product haven't any substantial connection having consumer novelty seeking for (early adoption with the brand new products) although it is often witnessed that consumer novelty seeking for offers optimistic have an effect on the consumer novelty seeking for that is the early on adoption with the product.

Nonetheless, desire for unique consumer product seriously isn't mediating the relationship between consumer innovativeness and also consumer novelty seeking for and also in the same manner definitely not enjoying a mediating part between consumer innovativeness and also consumer independent judgement making

Limitation and Recommendations

This particular review can't be the actual rep with the full populace regarding Pakistan because data may be accumulated on the students, and is particularly depicting the new product adoption habits with the students. Additional that is unable to resemble the actual older customers. It is strongly proposed regarding even more research that data needs to be accumulated on the older people as well as a comparison regarding students and also older people could be assessed. Investigation may also be done to research influence regarding group variables with new product adoption behavior.

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